

How to Use Corporate Education Tools to Reduce Ableism

Como Utilizar as Ferramentas da Educação Corporativa para a Redução do Capacitismo
Cómo utilizar las herramientas de educación corporativa para reducir el capacitismo

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Abstract: *This article, highlighted the relationship between corporate education tools and the reduction of ableism was highlighted. The inclusion of PWDs is ensured through quotas, which is known to society; however, an accessible workplace and, most importantly, opportunities for growth and professional development for these employees do not often occur. Prejudice and differential treatment towards people with disabilities make this inclusion, guaranteed by law and sought to enhance the employer's brand image, illusory. Corporate education aims to provide training, courses, and learning programs tailored to the specific needs of employees and the company. This may include technical skills related to job functions, as well as behavioral and leadership skills. Therefore, it is possible to use corporate education tools as a means of raising awareness among professionals who work with, live with, and lead PWDs, as well as to train and develop these professionals. This can be done through in-person activities such as lectures and mentorship, or through digital means, such as gamification and learning paths. Considering the above, the organization will benefit from greater diversity, which directly impacts its performance positively, as well as strengthens its image in society and among customers. As a result, both financial indicators (revenue, profit) of the company will show good results, as well as non-monetary indicators (absenteeism, organizational climate).*

Keywords: *Corporate education; Person with Disabilities (PwD); Ableism; Corporate education tools.*

Resumo: Este artigo, destacou a relação entre as ferramentas de educação corporativa e a redução do capacitismo. A inclusão de PcDs é assegurada por meio de cotas, o que é conhecido pela sociedade; no entanto, um ambiente de trabalho acessível e, mais importante, oportunidades de crescimento e desenvolvimento profissional para esses colaboradores não costumam ocorrer com frequência. O preconceito e o tratamento diferenciado em relação às pessoas com deficiência fazem com que essa inclusão, garantida por lei e buscada para aprimorar a imagem do empregador, seja ilusória. A educação corporativa visa fornecer treinamentos, cursos e programas de aprendizado adaptados às necessidades específicas dos funcionários e da empresa. Isso pode incluir desde habilidades técnicas relacionadas às funções desempenhadas

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até habilidades comportamentais e de liderança. Portanto, é possível utilizar as ferramentas de educação corporativa como meio de conscientização entre os profissionais que trabalham, convivem e lideram PcDs, bem como para treinar e desenvolver esses profissionais. Isso pode ser feito por meio de atividades presenciais, como palestras e mentorias, ou por meios digitais, como gamificação e trilhas de aprendizado. Diante do exposto, a organização se beneficiará com uma maior diversidade, o que impacta diretamente positivamente em seu desempenho, bem como fortalece sua imagem na sociedade e entre os clientes. Como resultado, os indicadores financeiros (receita, lucro) da empresa mostrarão bons resultados, bem como os indicadores não monetários (absenteísmo, clima organizacional).

Palavras-chave: Educação corporativa; Pessoa com deficiência (PCD); Capacitismo; Ferramentas da educação corporativa.

Resumen: Este artículo destacó la relación entre las herramientas de educación corporativa y la reducción del capacitismo. La inclusión de las Pcd se asegura a través de cuotas, lo cual es conocido por la sociedad; Sin embargo, no suele haber un entorno de trabajo accesible y, lo que es más importante, oportunidades de crecimiento y desarrollo profesional para estos empleados. Los prejuicios y el trato diferenciado en relación a las personas con discapacidad hacen ilusoria esta inclusión, garantizada por la ley y que busca mejorar la imagen del empleador. La educación corporativa tiene como objetivo proporcionar capacitación, cursos y programas de aprendizaje que se adapten a las necesidades específicas de los empleados y la empresa. Esto puede incluir cualquier cosa, desde habilidades técnicas relacionadas con los roles desempeñados hasta habilidades de comportamiento y liderazgo. Por lo tanto, es posible utilizar las herramientas de educación corporativa como un medio para sensibilizar a los profesionales que trabajan, conviven y lideran las Pcd, así como para formar y desarrollar a estos profesionales. Esto se puede hacer a través de actividades presenciales, como conferencias y mentorías, o a través de medios digitales, como la gamificación y las rutas de aprendizaje. En vista de lo anterior, la organización se beneficiará de una mayor diversidad, lo que impacta directamente en su desempeño, así como fortalece su imagen en la sociedad y entre los clientes. Como resultado, los indicadores financieros de la empresa (ingresos, ganancias) mostrarán buenos resultados, así como los indicadores no monetarios (ausentismo, clima organizacional).

Palabras clave: Educación corporativa; Personas con discapacidad (PCD); Capacitismo; Herramientas de educación corporativa.

1. INTRODUCTION

Permeated by frequent and unstable changes, the business environment requires members to have a great sense of adaptation and continuous learning. In this context, corporate education plays a crucial role, being defined as an educational process intrinsically linked to the strategic objectives of the organization, Aniceto (2009) and materialized through the structure of the corporate university. Aniceto (2009) also highlights that adequately trained workers are considered, in addition to strategic elements, extremely significant instruments for the interests of an organization; they become a relevant topic, therefore, for successful companies that understand the importance of their employees in terms of performance and innovations to be implemented in the work environment. It is clear, however, that corporate education should not be limited to technical skills alone but should also encompass a deep understanding of social issues, such as ableism, as discussed in the second paragraph. The intersection between corporate education and the reduction of ableism represents a significant opportunity for companies to strengthen their teams and promote an inclusive and conscious culture. Therefore, the research question on how to use corporate education tools to reduce ableism becomes central to addressing the challenges faced by people with disabilities in the workplace and promoting true equality and inclusion.

Ableism has become a widely discussed topic in the current decade. Although there are passages in the current law that guarantee the protection of PwDs against this injurious type of prejudice, such as Law No. 13,146, which in its Article 1 establishes that it must, through this law, "ensure and promote, under conditions of equality, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by people with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and citizenship," the implementation of the aforementioned legal provision lacks effectiveness in the social sphere. In the current organizational context, the company's image is essential in the eyes of society. In other words, in addition to healthy financial indicators, how people see organizations affects their functioning and performance. Given this, hiring people with disabilities occurs much more to comply with the law and to enhance their employer branding (employer brand credibility), and, therefore, they tend to occupy low-level positions with no opportunity for growth. In line with this thesis, companies are okay with preparing a physical and corporate structure to receive and retain these professionals. It is the organization's responsibility to adapt the workplace for people with disabilities and promote the same conditions that their colleagues without disabilities receive (LIMA, 2021).

Given the above, this article aims to investigate ways to reduce ableism in the job market and, consequently, analyze the view of people with disabilities and managers regarding the problem presented. Given this, the guiding question is: "How to use corporate education tools to reduce ableism?". Corporate education tools can help change this prejudiced scenario. Corporate education impacts professional growth through continuous learning and values the company's staff, even contributing to reducing absenteeism and turnover. This would allow PwDs to occupy leadership positions and not represent a quota to be filled.

For meaningful learning to occur in corporate education, the teaching processes in companies must be more inclusive regarding new knowledge, considering the importance of individuals' prior knowledge (LANGHI et al., 2021, Our translation).

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Corporate Education

The introductory knowledge is the understanding of Matos and Forte (2020), who emphasize that the emergence of Corporate Education only occurred between 1940 and 1950 in the United States, while the theme only developed on national soil in 1990. At the same time, Toledo (2018) understands that the breadth of the theme “education” has been valuable within organizations since the early 1990s, with the emergence of figures seeking dialogue and consideration about various areas of knowledge. This interaction between different information and areas that are not always so correlated, which we call the “Knowledge Society,” brought with it the metamorphosis of education, which was shaped and transformed into a fundamental gear for companies to move away from an outdated model and move towards modernizing their processes, becoming innovative and adaptable to the competitiveness imposed by the globalization of business. It is important to emphasize how this area suffered undeniable neglect in the business environment since the lack of reliability still made it ineffective in the market, being considered costly and, in some cases, even unnecessary. (TOLEDO, 2018).

Initially, corporate education began through the institution of management training and career self-management (TOLEDO, 2018). The author Eboli (1999) also highlights that corporate education was born with the proposal of making individuals capable enough to understand, interpret, and share the knowledge acquired for the benefit of organizations, adequately developing the sense of leadership and entrepreneurial thinking of these employees; a genuinely timeless idea, considering the number of successful companies that make fierce use of this tool to strengthen their human capital. It is known, therefore, that “organizational knowledge integrated between individuals, technologies, and processes is defended as the key to creating value” (TEECE, 2000).

2.2 Ableism in organizations

It is known that, in the current scenario, there is an incessant search for innovation and dynamism in the corporate world, with a focus on competitiveness and assertiveness in hiring employees. However, in the practice of retaining the best talent, most recruiters end up closing their eyes when it comes to the inclusion and diversity of their candidates (SOUZA et al, 2022). The term ableism has been used since 2012 as a way of naming the prejudice suffered by PcDs. This discrimination is actively and daily exposed, for example, in derogatory terms when referring to these individuals, in insults, and, often, in non-accessible architecture.

Due to the current quota system managed by the Brazilian Inclusion Law (Law

No. 13,146/2015), the recruitment and selection of PcDs has become mandatory in companies. However, what should be a factor generating equality in a society, especially in the corporate environment, has become a problem. Through reports and facts, it has been found that these professionals are selected only by complying with the law, and, in most cases, an outdated and prejudiced society is perceived, with constant judgmental looks and masked ableism directed at these people. Souza et al. (2022) emphasize that there is an essential need for more rigorous monitoring of this quota system, so it is duly complied with.

In agreement, Rezende (2013) reports that the fundamental factors for changes in these cases are the acceptance and cooperation of non-disabled employees and the implementation of inclusive practices managed by the HR department of organizations, ensuring that, currently, several awareness programs develop the culture of literacy on the topic of "social inclusion." Including people with disabilities in the job market is essential for the diversification of ideas and inclusion in general. However, this act carries an even greater baggage, a personal achievement for these individuals. Their inclusion in an organization is a factor that generates dignity and self-fulfillment.

When present in an organization, Inclusive Corporate Education establishes a relationship of respect between PwDs and the work environment. Sanches et al. (2022) state that these platforms must offer specific resources to these people, such as specialized educational support, trained professionals, and an organized education system, thus meeting the demands of these individuals and equally promoting the development of their skills.

2.3 Corporate Education Tools Aimed at Reducing Ableism

Corporate education, as already conceptualized throughout the article, provides employee development, improves the quality of work, retains talent, strengthens the organizational culture, and drives innovation. It is a strategic investment that brings benefits to both the individual and the company as a whole (CORREIA, 2018). However, we can turn corporate education tools to other problems that exist in the organizational environment. In addition to being used with PwD employees so that they develop, feel valued, receive growth opportunities, and are aligned with the company's culture, mission, vision, and values, it is possible to raise awareness among other employees about the difficulties of being a PwD and, consequently, increasingly reduce ableism.

The tools can vary according to the organization's needs. In this specific case, which aims to raise awareness and inclusion, in-person activities are more suitable for achieving a more significant impact. Therefore, the development of in-person lectures and training, mentoring, leadership development programs (in this case, the focal point would be the manager, focusing on what precautions he or she should take to manage this professional), and seeking an employee assessment of the activities is essential for the continuous improvement of processes. It does not mean that all programs must be in-person; it is also possible to take advantage of digital media for online programs that seek the development and growth of PwD employees. Gamification (the use of game

elements, such as challenges, rewards, and competitions, to make learning more engaging and interactive) can be interesting and more accepted by employees, in addition to e-learning, which are training modules done digitally and at the employee's pace (MATOS et al., 2017).

Finally, it is worth considering that, for an organization to obtain results, the internal customer (employees) must be as valued as the external customer. Because of this, corporate education also serves as a motivating factor and results in talent retention. In agreement with this thesis, it was proven in the theory of human relations, created by Elton Mayo from the Hawthorne experiment in the 19th century, where it was noticed that employees have more excellent performance if the work is done in a group and when they participate in decisions, that is, the benefit is not only monetary but also non-monetary (MAXIMINIANO, 2012).

2.3 Corporate Education Tools Aimed at Reducing Ableism

The issue of inclusion of people with disabilities (PwDs) is gaining increasing prominence in society's daily life. After a long history of marginalization, individuals with disabilities have come together in the search for the whole exercise of citizenship, asserting their place in the community and demanding access to all its resources and services (SHIMONO, 2008). However, there is still great prejudice and discrimination against people with disabilities in various contexts, especially in the workplace.

It is known that many organizations hire people with disabilities to meet legal quotas since failure to comply with this law results in punishment for these companies. However, according to Silva, Prais, and Silveira (2014), most companies demonstrate their prejudice and discrimination by seeking to hire people with disabilities considered "mild" because, according to these managers, the integration of these people would be easier. Moreover, with this, the ableist thinking of these managers becomes clear.

Ableism consists of constant doubts about the ability of a person with a disability to carry out their activities, whether in everyday life or the workplace. In this context, it seems that we are continually depriving people with disabilities of the opportunity to take on the leading role in their life journey. This deprivation occurs persistently throughout their lives and is reflected in discriminatory actions in everyday life, which devalue the person without even considering their true capabilities and completely denying their potential (PEREIRA, 2021).

It is known that not all people have had an inclusive education, having little or no contact with PwDs, so it would be essential to implement lectures and training on how to manage PwDs in companies and have an environment suitable for receiving employees with disabilities (SILVA; PRAIS; SILVEIRA, 2014). Moreover, for better assertiveness, it is essential to listen to people with disabilities, as there is a valuable opportunity for companies to explore accessibility by actively involving all interested parties in collaborating. This is because the search for inclusion is an ongoing process requiring constant improvement as new barriers

and challenges arise in users' daily lives (BORGES and LONGEN, 2019).

3. METHOD

A basic qualitative research approach was considered the best option for this article. Therefore, data were collected through interviews (conducted with the participant's permission) that were recorded and transcribed verbatim to ensure complete absorption of the results, which were later analyzed using Flores' category analysis technique (1994). The number of participants was defined by the theoretical saturation criterion, with the participation of managers and people with disabilities so that their respective views on the topic presented could be investigated. Thus, we sought to understand and analyze both perspectives, as shown below:

Chart 1 – Interviewees

Participants		Age	Company Segment	Position
PwD	R1 - Katariny Bueno Alves	25	Finance	User Experience Designer
	R4 - Raphael Herber	40	Technology	HR Assistant
Managers	R2 - Jessica de Luca	29	Telemarketing	BackOffice Supervisor
	R3 - Luciana Rocha	44	Retail	Human Resources Administration Manager

Source: Prepared by the authors (2023)

4. RESULTADOS E DISCUSSÃO

Chart 2 – Metacategory: "About the relationship"

Code	Category Definition	Units
TTM	Treatment	<p>R1 - I did not feel that I was treated unequally at any time in this company. I have felt that in another company I worked for, where... I was not well received after I had an accident that made me disabled, but in my current company, it has been very calm, yeah... people treat me as an equal, which is good.</p> <p>R3 - Fortunately, I have never witnessed any terminations, you know, with these professionals. However, there are managers and people who are not qualified to work in an environment with PWDs.</p> <p>R4 - In the past, the inequality and treatment were worse, it seemed like I didn't have the capacity, the knowledge, or the respect. (...) in general, that is how it is; they looked at me like I was poor, you know? They did not provide the services that other people had. "Take the basics from here," Keep doing this, and you will be fine" (...).</p>

DIM	Difficulties in Management	<p>R1 - I have never had any difficulty managing these professionals. In fact, in my last leadership role with a person with disabilities, I had a professional who knew nothing about HR. So, my inclusion was much greater with this professional because he did not have the knowledge I needed for the area. We started on a path of evolution; this professional now works in HR. This is a great satisfaction for me as a manager, okay?</p>
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Source: Prepared by the authors (2023)

The perspectives of PwDs and managers on the treatment that people with disabilities receive in companies offer valuable insights into reducing ableism. It's clear that, in certain areas, positive progress in promoting equal treatment is being made in the current companies of the PwDs interviewed. They state that they do not feel treated unequally and that they are welcomed in a satisfactory manner. Such observations underscore the empowering role of corporate education tools, such as training and awareness programs, in promoting inclusion and raising awareness about the needs of PwDs. This should motivate us to act and continue and expand these efforts.

However, managers recognize the existence of persistent problems, such as leaders who are not trained to deal with differences, highlighting the continued need for training and awareness programs. A manager's statement about the successful inclusion of an employee with a disability, despite his initial lack of HR knowledge, is a positive example. For instance, [provide a specific example of successful inclusion]. Therefore, corporate education can play a significant role in training managers to deal with diversity and inclusion, thus reducing ableism in companies.

Chart 3 – Metacategory: "Opportunity and development"

Code	Category definitio	Units
OPTFPWD	Opportunities for PwD	<p>R1 - In general, no... I think it depends a lot on the company's culture, and so, speaking for myself, for example, in my area, I feel that maybe I have it, but I see that talking to people from other areas, for example, from the bank, they do feel that there is a difference in treatment. I did not get to talk to them in-depth, but in general, there is a difference in treatment and inequality in the possibility of growth in the company. Most people stay in a function, in a position, you know, as a junior, and they do not have the visibility to move up to full senior precisely because they stagnate. They prefer... other people to occupy these positions, who are not PwD.</p> <p>R4 - In the past, there used to be no access ramps or handrails, you know those things? I went to work at an Itaú branch, and they didn't hire wheelchair users because there was no accessibility for them. Nowadays, companies are more concerned about this, and things are improving in this area.</p>

AAES	Actions aimed at enhancing skills.	<p>R1 - Ah, of course, not only in positions for people with disabilities but also in positions for people without disabilities. Making the... uh... get the person to study and get them ready to take the next step is extremely important for anyone's career, especially for people who do not have much assistance.</p> <p>R4 - In my opinion, no. It depends a lot on each person's development. The professional must be qualified and understand the subject, and nothing prevents them from holding a position of trust.</p>
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Source: Prepared by the authors (2023)

The meta categories presented in this third table focus on growth and career development opportunities for people with disabilities. The statements from people with disabilities express concerns about inequalities in opportunities for promotion and career advancement. They feel they are kept in junior positions and have less visibility to move up. It suggests that barriers to the professional growth of people with disabilities still need to be overcome, and the emphasis on actions aimed at developing skills indicates the importance of corporate education in training them. The statements from managers highlight the need for individual preparation and knowledge to take advantage of career development opportunities. Therefore, corporate education is crucial in training people with disabilities, providing them with the skills and knowledge necessary to overcome barriers to professional growth.

Chart 4 – Metacategory: "Corporate Education and Accessibility"

Code	Category Definition	Units
RA	Resource Accessibility	<p>R1 - Yes, there is a platform that we can request. It is some objects, right, for accessibility, whether for people with low vision or people with reduced mobility. They have a platform to make these requests and help according to their needs.</p> <p>R4 - In the past, there used to be no access ramps or handrails, you know those things? I went to work at an Itaú branch, and there, they didn't hire wheelchair users because there was no accessibility for them. Nowadays, companies are more concerned about this, and they are improving in this area.</p>
IOCE	Importance of Corporate Education.	<p>R1 - Of course, I think this is essential because many employees do not know how to deal with a person with a disability; it is... from sometimes making a joke or, it is... using terms in everyday life in a derogatory way, right? Using ableism is... to talk to people, or even using terms that can... hurt, right, the... the person, leave the person hurt. So I think that yes... in the corporate environment there should be this education, so that people learn, right, that maybe... maybe not, that this is not good, this is not cool, and... and I see that, for example, this</p>

		<p>happens in my work, daily, there are a lot of online meetings on the topic of diversity, ableism, yes... people with disabilities, LGBTQIA+.</p> <p>R2 - I think that every action, to... empower and encourage, yes... develop, every action is welcome and causes a vital impact... which I think is what is missing today.</p> <p>R3 - Yes! We need to be increasingly inclusive so that ableism does not affect our employee base. Corporate education has adequate tools for this.</p> <p>R4 - Corporate education is very important, but it must have the good will of the disabled employee, for example. The person must be dedicated to studying and training. It's no use just having the company provide it.</p>
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Source: Prepared by the authors (2023)

This section, the fourth table, is dedicated to accessibility issues and highlights the crucial role of corporate education in combating ableism. The feedback from individuals with disabilities on accessibility enhancements, such as access ramps and handrails, is a testament to companies' commitment to fostering more inclusive work environments. The establishment of a platform for adaptation requests is a tangible demonstration of companies' dedication to prioritizing accessibility, thereby effecting real changes in inclusion practices and positively impacting organizational performance.

The importance of corporate education is evident in the stories of both individuals with disabilities and managers. The necessity of raising awareness among employees about the needs of individuals with disabilities, discouraging derogatory comments, and promoting an understanding of diversity is a key aspect. Meetings on diversity, ableism, and underrepresented groups are cited as beneficial practices, providing strong evidence that corporate education tools are pivotal in fostering an inclusive culture and reducing ableism.

5. CONCLUSION

In short, the relationship between the tools present in corporate education and the reduction of ableism was highlighted. It is generally accepted that the inclusion of people with disabilities in companies is ensured through quotas; however, the presence of an accessible location and opportunities for growth and professional development for these employees is not usually expected. Prejudice and the different treatment of people with disabilities make this inclusion guaranteed by law, which often arises solely from the search for brand potential, merely illusory. However, the positive impact of corporate education in reducing ableism offers hope for a more inclusive future.

Positive contributions concerning the management of current organizations can

be pointed out by considering the study carried out. Providing training, courses, and learning programs that are targeted to the specific needs of employees and the company can provide immense added value. It can include everything from technical skills related to the functions performed to behavioral and leadership skills. Therefore, it is possible to use corporate education tools to support the awareness of professionals who work with, live with, and lead people with disabilities, in addition to training and developing such individuals. The respective notes are only possible through in-person activities, such as lectures and mentoring, and digital activities, using resources such as gamification and learning trails. Aspects such as the lack of attention given to the preparation of future managers so that they can correctly support employees with some type of disability in the future and the lack of physical accessibility are still extremely and negatively striking factors and should be taken into consideration in future studies on the subject.

Given the above, if the appropriate adaptations and monitoring of the inclusion process are made, the organization will have greater diversity, which will directly (and positively) impact its performance, strengthening its image before society, customers, and the market. The importance of diversity in organizational performance cannot be overstated, underscoring the urgency of addressing ableism and fostering inclusion.

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